

The potential of pamrevlumab in diseases with underlying mechanisms of fibrotic processes and its prospects in ophthalmology

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Abstract

Introduction: Pamrevlumab, a monoclonal antibody targeting CTGF, is considered a potential therapy for eye diseases involving fibrosis. The aim of this study was to explore its potential in treating eye diseases.

Methods: A systematic review was conducted following PRISMA guidelines, searching studies up to 2024 across various databases. Study quality was assessed using the Cochrane RoB 2.0 tool.

Results: Pamrevlumab has the potential to slow fibrosis progression and improve organ function, although treatment responses varied. Two studies showed significant changes, while four did not. The risk of bias indicated varied methodological quality.

Discussion: Pamrevlumab shows potential in treating fibrosis-related eye diseases by inhibiting CTGF. Further research is needed to assess its long-term effects, safety, and dose optimization.

Conclusion: Pamrevlumab shows significant potential in the treatment of chronic eye diseases, with promising safety outcomes based on previous experiences in DMD patients.

Keywords

connective tissue growth factor, fibrosis, monoclonal antibody, systematic review

Introduction

Ophthalmology has advanced significantly with new therapies for various eye conditions. Pamrevlumab, a monoclonal antibody targeting connective tissue growth factor (CTGF), shows promise in managing ocular dis-

eases involving fibrosis and inflammation, such as proliferative diabetic retinopathy and macular degeneration (Rodrigues et al. 2009). CTGF, a critical mediator in fibrosis, is elevated in many eye disorders, making it a vital therapeutic target (Dillinger et al. 2023). Developed by FibroGen, pamrevlumab inhibits CTGF activity, potentially

reversing fibrosis and offering hope for patients unresponsive to VEGF- or TGF- β -targeted treatments. Early trials demonstrate its safety and efficacy, warranting further investigation (Kuijper 2006; Raghu et al. 2024).

Methods

Study design and search strategy

This systematic review was conducted based on the checklist from the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA; Page et al. 2021). Articles published up to 2024 were retrieved if they assessed the potential of pamrevlumab in diseases with fibrotic mechanisms. The search was conducted using databases including PubMed, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, Springer Nature, Cochrane, and Wiley Online Library.

Studies on fibrotic diseases were included if they involved a diagnostic process with either one or two groups. For therapy-related studies, preference was given to those structured with an “intervention” group and a “control” group. The keywords used in the article search were (“pamrevlumab” OR “FG-3019”) AND (“fibrosis” OR “fibrotic disease” OR “fibrotic disorders”) AND (“treatment” OR “therapy” OR “intervention” OR “comparative”) AND (“effectiveness” OR “efficacy” OR “outcome” OR “progression” OR “slowing” OR “inhibition” OR “side effects”) AND (“potential” OR “prospects” OR “application” OR “efficacy” OR “effectiveness” OR “therapeutic use”). All retrieved information was analyzed to reach an accurate conclusion.

Study inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria were (1) randomized controlled trials (RCTs) or observational studies (cross-sectional, cohort, case-control); (2) patients or study populations diagnosed with fibrotic diseases, whether systemic or related to eye conditions; (3) no age or gender restrictions on the study population; and (4) studies reporting outcomes regarding pamrevlumab. Exclusion criteria were (1) duplicate publications, (2) studies not published in English, and (3) studies not reporting the desired outcomes. All studies were reviewed and discussed among the authors to assess eligibility for inclusion in the systematic review. The expected outcome was to determine the effectiveness of pamrevlumab in slowing or inhibiting fibrosis progression.

Study selection

After initial screening based on titles and abstracts, two reviewers (LEL and BOW) independently selected studies using the predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Covidence was used to extract relevant data and remove duplicates. Keywords were used to identify terms relevant to inclusion and exclusion criteria within the platform.

Disagreements regarding study inclusion were resolved through discussion and consultation with a third reviewer (DAY). Full-text screening was then performed, with two

reviewers (LEL and BOW) independently evaluating studies for final inclusion. Any further disagreement was resolved by consensus in consultation with the third reviewer (DAY).

Data extraction study quality assessment

The data extraction process was conducted by filtering the literature according to the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The extracted information included (1) study name and publication year, (2) title, (3) study design, (4) number of participants, (5) intervention, (6) comparison, and (7) outcomes or study results. Data evaluation followed the criteria outlined in the “Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions”. To assess the quality of studies included in the systematic review, the Cochrane RoB 2.0 tool was applied, which evaluates potential biases across various domains, including selection, performance, detection, reporting, attrition, and other sources of bias specific to randomized controlled trials (Sterne et al. 2019). Two independent reviewers assessed the risk of bias in each study, considering the specific criteria and guidelines provided by the Cochrane RoB 2.0 tool. Discrepancies between reviewers were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer. The methodological components of each trial were classified as having low, high, or unclear risk of bias, in accordance with the Cochrane Handbook (Higgins et al. 2024). Changes in the quality of evidence will be summarized in a findings table to provide transparency and justification for each bias assessment.

Result

Study selection

From the entire database, we successfully narrowed down the collection of articles to 182 studies. After a thorough examination, 30 duplicate articles were removed. A total of 152 publications were selected for further review after the initial screening of titles and abstracts. Then, 29 studies were obtained, followed by the collection of full texts. Based on the abstract and full text, we excluded 22 articles, with 11 of them not matching the desired sample population, 7 using inappropriate studies, 2 studies with incorrect interventions, and 2 studies with inappropriate outcomes. After determining the feasibility and quality of the filtered full-text articles, 7 articles were finally selected for the systematic review process. Fig. 1 shows the PRISMA flow diagram illustrating the study selection procedure.

Characteristics and study results

Of the seven selected studies, each investigated the administration of pamrevlumab as a potential treatment for fibrotic diseases. The studies were conducted in two regions: the United States and Europe. They were categorized based on the primary variable – administration of

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram generated using Covidence.

pamrevlumab for fibrotic conditions. The fibrotic diseases included Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD), idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), COVID-19 pneumonia, and diabetes with microalbuminuria. Almost all studies reported that pamrevlumab consistently slowed fibrosis progression and improved the function of affected organs, although not all demonstrated statistically significant results (Table 1). However, it is important to consider that the effectiveness of pamrevlumab may vary due to individual differences in genetics, underlying health conditions, and other uncontrolled factors within the study designs.

Evaluation of study method quality

The Cochrane Risk of Bias (RoB 2.0) tool was used to assess the methodological quality and risk of bias in the included studies (Fig. 2). The effectiveness of pamrevlumab varied considerably across the studies. Study durations ranged from several days to several years. Two studies (28.5%) showed significant therapeutic effects, while four studies (57.2%) did not demonstrate statistically significant outcomes. One study (14.2%) reported a favorable safety profile for pamrevlumab, with no observed adverse effects.

Table 1. Characteristics and study results.

No	Study, years	Title	Study Design	Total Subject		Intervention	Comparison	Outcome
				Intervention	Control			
1.	Adler et al. 2010. ⁷	Phase I study of anti-CTGF monoclonal antibody in patients with diabetes and microalbuminuria	Open-label, randomized, dose-escalation trial, but not placebo-controlled or blinded.	24		Pamrevlumab infusions at two different doses: 3 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg (administered every 14 days for a total of 56 days (on days 0, 14, 28, and 42))	The study did not include a control population receiving a placebo.	Pamrevlumab has been shown to be safe and well-tolerated during the 6-week treatment period. No subjects developed anti-pamrevlumab antibodies, and reported side effects were generally mild to moderate. There was a significant decrease in ACR in patients receiving pamrevlumab, particularly in those with higher baseline microalbuminuria. This reduction indicates the potential of pamrevlumab to decrease urinary albumin excretion, an important indicator of kidney damage. HbA1c levels remained stable throughout the treatment period, suggesting that pamrevlumab did not negatively impact the patients' glycemic control. Plasma CTGF N-fragment showed a significant increase following pamrevlumab infusions, which may reflect the drug's influence on CTGF metabolism in the body.
2.	Raghu et al. 2016. ⁸	FG-3019 anti-connective tissue growth factor monoclonal antibody: results of an open-label clinical trial in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis	Open-label, single-arm, multi-center, phase 2a clinical trial.	89		Pamrevlumab was administered via intravenous infusion every 3 weeks to patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) over a 45-week study period.	The study did not include a control population receiving a placebo.	Pamrevlumab demonstrated a good safety profile, with side effects mostly being mild and tolerable for patients. The average forced vital capacity (FVC) of patients decreased by 140 mL after 48 weeks of treatment. Approximately 30% of patients experienced an increase in FVC, while 13.6% had a decrease in FVC of 10% or more. Some patients showed a reduction in reticular fibrosis scores after 48 weeks. Patients with stable or reduced fibrosis tended to experience an increase in FVC, whereas those with increased fibrosis experienced a decrease in FVC.
3.	Richeldi et al. 2019. ⁹	Pamrevlumab, an anti-connective tissue growth factor therapy, for idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (PRAISE): a phase 2, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial	Phase 2, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multi-site clinical trial.	50	53	Pamrevlumab group: 30 mg/kg dose via IV every 3 weeks (16 infusions over 48 weeks)	Placebo Group: Received identical frequency and amount of infusions.	Pamrevlumab reduced the decline in percentage of predicted forced vital capacity (FVC) by 60.3% compared to placebo at week 48. The proportion of patients with disease progression (decline in FVC \geq 10% or death) was lower in the pamrevlumab group compared to placebo at week 48 (10.0% vs 31.4%). Pamrevlumab was well-tolerated, with a similar safety profile to placebo.
4.	Connolly et al. 2023. ¹⁰	Pamrevlumab, a fully human monoclonal antibody targeting connective tissue growth factor, for non-ambulatory patients with Duchenne muscular dystrophy	Open-label, Phase II, single-arm trial	21		All patients received intravenous infusions of pamrevlumab at a dose of 35 mg/kg every two weeks over a two-year period.	The study did not include a control population receiving a placebo.	The study shows that treatment with pamrevlumab is associated with a slower decline in muscle function, as measured by percent predicted forced vital capacity (ppFVC) and other assessments. This suggests that by reducing fibrotic processes, pamrevlumab may help maintain muscle function for a longer period in non-ambulatory patients with Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD).

No	Study, years	Title	Study Design	Total Subject		Intervention	Comparison	Outcome
				Intervention	Control			
5.	Sgalla et al. 2023. ¹¹	A randomized trial of pamrevlumab in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia	Randomized-controlled trial	19	23	Pamrevlumab: at a dose of 30 mg/kg via intravenous infusion on day 1 (randomization), day 7, and day 14	Standard of Care (SOC): Remdesivir: Administered within 7 days after a positive PCR test Dexamethasone: 6 mg per day for 10 days. Low Molecular Weight Heparin: To prevent thrombosis.	The proportion of patients alive and not on mechanical ventilation at day 15 was similar between the pamrevlumab group and the standard of care (SOC) group. Patients receiving pamrevlumab showed an improvement in the PaO ₂ /FIO ₂ ratio; however, this difference was not statistically significant. Patients treated with pamrevlumab showed more radiological stability compared to the SOC group, although the difference was not statistically significant.
6.	Raghu et al. 2024. ³	Pamrevlumab for idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis: the Zephyrus-1 randomized clinical trial	Randomized controlled trial	181	175	Pamrevlumab, at a dose of 30 mg/kg, is given intravenously every 3 weeks for a duration of 48 weeks.	Placebo group: (intravenous infusion every 3 weeks) as a control.	Among patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, treatment with pamrevlumab did not result in a significantly slower decline in forced vital capacity compared to placebo over 48 weeks. There were no significant differences between the pamrevlumab and placebo groups for secondary or exploratory outcomes measured. The safety profile of pamrevlumab was similar to that of placebo, with no increase in the frequency of adverse events.
7.	Raghu et al. 2016. ⁸	Pamrevlumab for idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis: results of the phase 3 Zephyrus-1 study	Phase 3 randomized, placebo-controlled, and double-blind trial known as ZEPHYRUS-1	181	175	Pamrevlumab: Administered at a dose of 30 mg/kg via intravenous infusion every 3 weeks for a duration of 48 weeks.	Placebo group: Administered in the same manner (intravenous infusion every 3 weeks) as a control.	The study did not meet the primary efficacy endpoint, indicating that pamrevlumab did not provide a significant benefit compared to placebo. Although not statistically significant, the results showed a trend toward improvement in time to disease progression and some patient-reported outcomes (PROs) that tended to be better with pamrevlumab. Pamrevlumab demonstrated good tolerability, with similar incidence rates of adverse events between the groups receiving pamrevlumab and placebo.

Study ID	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall	
Sharon, 2010	+	-	+	-	!	-	+ Low risk
Raghu, 2016	-	!	+	-	+	-	! Some concerns
Richeldi, 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+	- High risk
Connolly, 2023	-	+	+	-	!	-	
Sgalla, 2023	+	-	-	-	+	-	D1 Randomisation process
Raghu, 2024a	+	!	+	+	+	+	D2 Deviations from the intended interventions
Raghu, 2024b	+	-	!	+	+	-	D3 Missing outcome data
							D4 Measurement of the outcome
							D5 Selection of the reported result

Figure 2. Risk of bias assessment by Cochrane Risk of Bias (RoB 2.0).

Discussion

Biomolecular of pamrevlumab

Pamrevlumab, initially designated FG-3019, is a fully humanized monoclonal antibody targeting CTGF/CCN2 (FibroGen, Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA). Its mechanism of action involves binding to the von Willibrand factor type C (vWC) domain of the CCN2 protein, which interacts with transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β). Pamrevlumab thus functions as a direct inhibitor of the CCN2-TGF- β interaction (Fig. 3) (Ramazani et al. 2018).

(Pamrevlumab disrupts TGF- β -mediated signaling by inhibiting CTGF binding to EGFR, NTRK1, integrins, and LRP6/LRP1, thereby attenuating inflammation, inhibiting excessive fibrosis via ECM modulation, and suppressing cellular proliferation through the regulation of SMAD, ERK, NF- κ B, and KLF10 pathways.)

Mechanism of action of pamrevlumab

Pamrevlumab is a fully human recombinant antibody that binds specifically to CTGF, preventing its interaction with cytokines and downstream inflammatory signaling. CTGF is a secreted glycoprotein produced by fibroblasts, myofibroblasts, endothelial cells, and other cell types. It functions as a multifunctional signaling molecule involved in angiogenesis, osteogenesis, kidney disorders, dermal pathologies, and tumorigenesis (Raghu et al. 2024). CTGF is upregulated in various fibrotic lesions and exerts mitogenic and chemotactic effects on fibroblasts. It also enhances mRNA expression of collagen α 1, fibronectin, and integrin α 5 in fibroblasts. TGF- β promotes CTGF synthesis, and their overlapping functions suggest that CTGF may act as a downstream mediator of TGF- β activity (Chu et al. 2008).

CTGF interacts with regulatory modulators such as TGF- β , VEGF, and integrin receptors. The synergy between TGF- β and CTGF amplifies the fibrotic cascade,

Figure 3. Biomolecular mechanism of pamrevlumab.

positioning CTGF as a critical therapeutic target in fibrotic disorders. Pamrevlumab interferes with this axis, potentially stabilizing or reversing fibrotic processes in affected tissues (Richeldi et al. 2020). CTGF modulates extracellular matrix organization, cellular secretion, motility, and adhesion – biological behaviors associated with tissue remodeling, tumor development, and fibrotic progression (Richeldi et al. 2020).

One principal function of CTGF is to support cell adhesion through integrin- and heparan sulfate proteoglycan-dependent mechanisms. The 10 kDa C-terminal domain of CTGF, which binds heparin, is sufficient to mediate cell adhesion and stimulate fibroblast proliferation. The type of integrin involved varies by cell type: integrin $\alpha6\beta1$ in skin fibroblasts, $\alpha11\beta3$ in platelets, $\alpha\nu\beta3$ in endothelial cells, and $\alpha M\beta2$ in monocytes (Hendesi et al. 2015).

The potential of pamrevlumab in other fibrotic diseases

Pamrevlumab has been evaluated in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) across four clinical studies. In the PRAISE trial – a phase 2 randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study – pamrevlumab demonstrated a 60.3% reduction in forced vital capacity (FVC) decline compared with placebo, suggesting its capacity to slow IPF progression (Richeldi et al. 2020). Notably, some patients showed

radiographic evidence of fibrosis reversal, marking a potential therapeutic breakthrough. However, the phase 3 ZEPHYRUS-1 trial did not find a statistically significant difference in FVC decline between pamrevlumab and placebo at 48 weeks, with an average difference of 70 mL ($P = 0.29$). Despite this, a trend toward prolonged time to disease progression and modest improvements in patient-reported outcomes (PROs) was observed, slightly favoring pamrevlumab (Raghu et al. 2024). In terms of safety, pamrevlumab was well tolerated in both the PRAISE and ZEPHYRUS-1 trials. Serious adverse events were reported in 28.2% of pamrevlumab-treated patients compared to 34.3% in the placebo group, indicating a comparable safety profile (Raghu et al. 2024). These findings highlight the variability in therapeutic response and suggest that while pamrevlumab may slow disease progression, it does not halt or cure IPF.

In Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD), all patients enrolled in this study are male, aged 12 years and older, and have a genetically confirmed diagnosis of DMD. The patients had previously received corticosteroid therapy. All patients received intravenous infusions of pamrevlumab at a dose of 35 mg/kg every two weeks for a period of two years. However, in this study, the researchers did not use a control group to compare their study, which could lead to biased results and make it difficult to accurately assess the true effectiveness of pamrevlumab. Additionally,

DMD has a highly variable disease course, which can affect the outcomes and make it challenging to draw definitive conclusions about the treatment's effectiveness. This study shows that treatment with pamrevlumab is associated with a slower decline in muscle function, as measured by ppFVC and other assessments. Thus, pamrevlumab may help maintain muscle function for a longer period in non-ambulatory patients with DMD.

In the case of COVID-19 pneumonia, a randomized controlled trial (RCT) design was conducted involving 42 patients, consisting of 19 patients who received pamrevlumab at a dose of 30 mg/kg through intravenous infusion on day 1 (randomization), day 7, and day 14, and 23 patients who only received Standard of Care (SOC) for 2 years. The SOC group received treatment with remdesivir, dexamethasone, and heparin. In this study, pamrevlumab did not show additional benefits compared to SOC in the treatment of COVID-19 pneumonia. Although some improvements were observed, such as in the PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio, these differences did not reach statistical significance.

In the study of diabetes and microalbuminuria, an open-label, randomized, dose-escalation trial design was conducted without a placebo control, involving 24 patients with type 1 or type 2 diabetes and microalbuminuria. Patients received pamrevlumab infusions at two different doses: 3 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg. Infusions were given every 14 days for a total of 56 days (days 0, 14, 28, and 42). The results showed a significant decrease in ACR in patients receiving pamrevlumab, especially in those with higher baseline microalbuminuria. This decrease indicates the potential of pamrevlumab in reducing urinary albumin excretion, which is an important indicator of kidney damage. In addition, HbA_{1c} levels remained stable during the treatment period, so pamrevlumab did not negatively impact the patients' glycemic control. No subjects developed antibodies against pamrevlumab, and the reported side effects were generally mild to moderate.

Some studies had a low quality of assessment, as there were three studies with an "open-label" design, meaning no blinding or concealment of intervention information was applied. Additionally, several studies had limitations in implementing interventions, such as incorrect dosing, participants discontinuing treatment midway, patients experiencing worsening conditions that required stopping the intervention, and small sample sizes, all of which contributed to bias in these studies. Furthermore, some studies lacked a control group for comparison, which could result in biased outcomes. Therefore, the studies included in the systematic review indicate a need for further, higher-quality research.

The potential of pamrevlumab in the field of ophthalmology

Pamrevlumab shows significant promise in treating idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis by slowing disease progression and improving lung function. Its mechanism of action, targeting CTGF, positions it as a potentially effective therapy for various fibrotic conditions. Ongoing phase 3 trials and further research will be crucial in establishing its role in the broader landscape of fibrosis treatment.

Pamrevlumab, by inhibiting CTGF, has the potential to reduce the pathological processes involved in diabetic retinopathy. CTGF interacts with other growth factors, particularly vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). In proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR), the balance between VEGF and CTGF is crucial; while VEGF promotes angiogenesis, elevated CTGF can shift the process from angiogenesis to fibrosis. This angiogenic-to-fibrotic transition is characterized by an excess of CTGF leading to the formation of fibrotic membranes, which contribute to complications such as tractional retinal detachment. Additionally, CTGF has been shown to inhibit VEGF-induced angiogenesis, indicating a complex feedback regulatory mechanism between these two factors (Kuiper 2006; Kuiper et al. 2008).

By targeting CTGF, pamrevlumab can decrease the production of extracellular matrix (ECM) components, thus reducing retinal fibrosis. This is critical in preventing retinal layer thickening, which can lead to vision impairment. Additionally, in proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR), the levels of CTGF in the vitreous humor are significantly correlated with the extent of intraocular fibrosis, indicating that CTGF is a major contributor to the fibrotic process that can result in vision loss (Kuiper 2006; Kuiper et al. 2008). Pamrevlumab targeting CTGF may also inhibit angiogenic pathways leading to neovascularization. By blocking signals that promote the growth of abnormal blood vessels, pamrevlumab can help prevent the progression from non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) to PDR. Moreover, it may help reduce the inflammatory response in the retina, leading to a decrease in retinal edema and overall improvement in retinal health (Zheng 2012).

Age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is often associated with fibrotic changes in the retina. AMD is a leading cause of vision loss in older adults, characterized by degeneration of the macula, the central part of the retina responsible for sharp vision. The pathophysiology of AMD involves several key processes, including inflammation, oxidative stress, and neovascularization (Roestenberg 2007). By targeting CTGF, pamrevlumab can reduce the production of extracellular matrix (ECM) components, thus limiting fibrosis and preventing retinal layer thickening that can interfere with vision (Higashijima et al. 2022). In advanced AMD, particularly in the wet form, abnormal blood vessel growth (neovascularization) occurs. CTGF plays a role in promoting angiogenesis, and by inhibiting CTGF, pamrevlumab can help prevent the development of these abnormal blood vessels, which could lead to further vision loss (Bai et al. 2016). Pamrevlumab can also help modulate the inflammatory response by reducing CTGF levels, which may decrease the recruitment of inflammatory cells and lower the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the retina (Pirani et al. 2020).

CTGF is also involved in the trans-differentiation of fibroblasts into myofibroblasts, which are key players in the fibrotic response. In conditions like Graves' ophthalmopathy (GO), CTGF mediates the production of extracellular matrix induced by TGF- β and the activation of myofibroblasts, leading to tissue remodeling and fibrosis. This pro-

cess can result in significant ocular complications, including motility restriction and proptosis (Tsai et al. 2018). In addition to its potential applications in diabetic retinopathy and age-related macular degeneration, pamrevlumab may also play an important role in addressing other ocular conditions characterized by similar pathological processes. For instance, the management of retinal vein occlusion (RVO), which is often associated with vascular changes and inflammation, could benefit from the anti-fibrotic and anti-inflammatory properties of pamrevlumab (Muniyandi et al. 2023). Since RVO can lead to significant vision loss due to edema and neovascularization, harnessing pamrevlumab's ability to inhibit CTGF could provide a new therapeutic approach, improving patient outcomes and preserving visual function over time.

As research progresses, it is crucial to consider not only the efficacy of pamrevlumab in treating eye conditions but also its safety profile and potential side effects. Clinical trials for Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD), which have provided insights into the drug's tolerability, revealed that participants experienced mild to moderate side effects without leading to discontinuation of treatment (Connolly et al. 2023). This suggests that similar safety outcomes can be anticipated in ophthalmic applications, potentially enabling long-term management of chronic eye diseases. Furthermore, understanding the pharmacokinetics of pamrevlumab will be essential in determining the optimal dosing regimen tailored to specific eye disorders, thereby maximizing therapeutic benefits while minimizing risks. As we delve further into these aspects, the integration of pamrevlumab into standard care practices for debilitating eye diseases appears increasingly promising.

Studies on the effectiveness of pamrevlumab have several limitations that should be considered for future research. Small sample sizes and variations in study design, including randomized trials and observational studies, restrict the broader applicability of results. The lack of long-term data also limits understanding of the safety and effectiveness of pamrevlumab over an extended period. Future studies are recommended to use double-blind, placebo-controlled trials to reduce bias, especially in open-label studies. Safety profile limitations and the absence of control groups in some studies make it difficult to evaluate effectiveness accurately, highlighting the need for control groups and control of confounding variables such as patient demographics and other therapies. Further research on the pharmacokinetics of pamrevlumab in the context of ocular diseases is also needed to optimize dosage and therapeutic benefits. By addressing these issues, future research is expected to strengthen the understanding of pamrevlumab's potential in treating fibrotic diseases, particularly in ophthalmology.

Conclusion

Pamrevlumab shows significant potential in the treatment of chronic eye diseases, with promising safety outcomes based on previous experiences in DMD patients.

Further research on the drug's pharmacokinetics and dosage adjustments for specific eye disorders will be key to optimizing therapy and enhancing patient quality of life. Thus, the integration of pamrevlumab into treatment protocols will pave the way for new approaches in eye disease management, enabling patients to gain the maximum benefit from this therapy and improving long-term outcomes. It is essential to continue in-depth clinical research to fully understand pamrevlumab's mechanism of action and potential benefits across various eye diseases, thus providing more effective treatment recommendations in the future.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Lely Retno Wulandari: Concepts, Design, Definition of intellectual content, Experimental studies, Statistical analysis, Manuscript preparation, Manuscript Review, Guarantor.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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